

Performance of hybrid quantum-classical computing architectures

Stanislaw Grodek

A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment
of the requirements for the degree of
MSc Quantum Technologies

Department of Physics and Astronomy
University College London

September 2023

Abstract

In the ever-changing world of quantum computing, this paper explores advancements in the current state-of-the-art of hybrid quantum-classical architectures and quantum algorithms. It proposes a roadmap classifier towards large-scale integration. A pivotal aspect of our exploration is the comparative benchmarking of QBoost and AdaBoost algorithms, aided by D-Wave Leap quantum annealers. The analysis is supported by standard performance metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. We demonstrate significant computational speed-up using binary classification datasets, exemplifying quantum advantage.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	2
1.1. Overview of the research.....	3
2. Hybrid Quantum-Classical Architectures	5
2.1. Roadmap Towards Large-Scale Integration.....	5
2.2. Loose Integration.....	10
2.2.1. Implementation of client-server model	11
2.3. Tight Integration.....	11
2.3.1. Implementation of the accelerator model.....	12
2.3.2. Implementation of the interconnected QPUs	12
3. Hybrid Quantum Algorithms	14
3.1. QAOA and VQE algorithms	14
3.2. Shor's algorithm.....	15
3.3. Variational quantum-classical algorithms for client-server model outlook	15
4. Experimental Results	16
4.1. Methodology	16
4.2. Four Metrics Discussion.....	18
4.3. Need for Speed	21
5. Conclusions	23

1. Introduction

Quantum computing has emerged as a promising solution for solving complex problems that cannot be solved analytically with classical computing techniques. By leveraging principles of quantum mechanics, like entanglement, superposition, and intrinsic randomness, exponential algorithmic speed-up can be achieved [1]. Quantum algorithms have demonstrated superior performance compared to classical counterparts, particularly for so-called benchmarking problems such as factoring integers and finding discrete logarithms, which are essential in modern public-key encryption [2]. Chemists have also conducted experiments utilising quantum adiabatic hardware to simulate lattice folding in the hydrophobic-polar model, a crucial drug discovery and development process. Additionally, researchers have simulated the H₂ molecule on linear-optical quantum computers, providing evidence of the potential of small-scale quantum computation [3]. Though scalability is a current limitation, the development of large-scale quantum computers can revolutionise virtually all industries, from finance and medical applications to security. Therefore, one can witness worldwide efforts to realise large-scale quantum computing technologies that can potentially become technological disruptors.

Richard Feynman coined this concept in the late 20th century, and researchers have worked relentlessly to bring this technology into reality ever since. In a recent milestone, Google achieved ‘quantum supremacy’ by creating a quantum circuit on a 54-qubit quantum processor in just 200 seconds. In perspective, a classical supercomputer would require about 10,000 years to perform the same calculation [4, 5]. Nevertheless, it is essential to note that numerous challenges must be addressed before quantum computing can become a practical and widely adopted tool.

To fully utilise the capabilities of quantum processing units (QPUs), it is crucial to integrate them with high-performance computing (HPC) architectures. HPC systems employ specialised accelerators to accommodate new processing paradigms [6]. As per a study by Chen et al. (2012), applying MapReduce techniques to CPU-GPU chips led to a substantial increase in computational speed compared to using only CPU or GPU chips [7], showcasing that a hybrid approach in constructing the network could enhance the best qualities from both worlds, in our case quantum and classical.

The benefits of the implementation, as mentioned above, are twofold. Firstly, the use of specialised hardware for low-level processes governing individual components in the network allows researchers to test their ideas without requiring extensive refactoring of the program [8].

This is particularly advantageous as it saves costs that would otherwise be incurred in manufacturing complex hardware that may not necessarily work in real-life applications [9]. Secondly, with the anticipation that technological progress will continue at a steady pace, emerging technologies can be leveraged regarding the accelerator model and its integrity in upcoming system development [10, 11].

1.1. Overview of the research

Now that we have established the reasons behind our research, it is important to clarify the scope of our study and detail the methods we have used. Our project is focused on evaluating the performance of hybrid quantum-classical computing architectures compared to their classical counterparts. To achieve this, we have utilised QBoost and AdaBoost algorithms as aids in benchmarking performance. As the name suggests, these algorithms are examples of boosting algorithms; in machine learning, this is achieved by carefully selecting a set of ‘weak’ predictors that combined act as a ‘strong’ one, effectively creating an ensemble model. Both of these algorithms work on the same premise. Initially, the dataset is split into training and testing samples. Within the training dataset, equal weights are assigned to all features, and at the first stage, the model employs decision stumps, i.e. one-level decision trees, to train the model based on the current weights. Then, the performance of each ‘weak’ classifier is evaluated. Following the lowest error rate, the best performing ‘weak’ classifiers are assigned higher weights to reinforce their vote on the overall ensemble classification [12].

Conversely, underperforming classifiers are tuned down to reduce the overall error rate of the model. After the first iteration, the algorithm assigns new weights, emphasising the misclassified samples so the new generation of ‘weak’ learners can outperform their predecessors. The above-described process is repeated until the desired accuracy is achieved or for a fixed number of iterations. The key is to focus each ‘weak’ learner on the difficult instances to classify them correctly, gradually increasing the model's ability to handle challenging cases. By combining the strengths of multiple ‘weak’ learners, the algorithm produces a robust ensemble model that frequently surpasses even some complex models, particularly in the context of classification [12].

Although the stem of these algorithms is the same, they differ in at least two main aspects, namely the loss function and hardware. As with all optimisation problems, the task is to minimise error between the predicted target and the actual result. QBoost achieves that by

employing a squared loss function that can be found in Neven et al. (2008) [13]. It is important to note that the squared loss function can be sensitive to outliers and may give too much weight to larger errors. However, this function has the advantage of yielding a well-behaved convex optimisation problem, leading to efficient and highly accurate solutions, which quantum annealers can leverage [13, 14]. QBoost's quantum part is revealed once the algorithm begins to search for optimal weights for its 'weak' learners. This optimisation task can be formulated as a quadratic unconstrained binary optimisation (QUBO) problem that, in turn, can be solved on quantum annealers [15-17]. The QUBO problem is translated into quantum mechanical language, and the system is adiabatically evolved to reach its ground state, thus the holistic solution. Speaking of quantum annealers, D-Wave is one of the major players in the quantum computing space, with their own hardware and an open-source IDE that allows developers to explore quantum computing with ease. Other companies such as IBM, Google or Rigetti all developed their own quantum hardware based on superconductive circuits, an approach that will be discussed in greater depth in subsequent *section 2.1*.

On the other hand, AdaBoost employs an exponential loss function discussed by Hastie et al. (2009) [18]. Irrespective of its mathematical representation, the goal of the loss function remains consistent. It aims to pinpoint the dataset instances where the algorithm faces challenges in accurate classification and aims to enhance its weaknesses through iterative refinement. Exponential loss function is a proxy function of 0-1 loss function, which is used in classification problems to evaluate the accuracy of predictions. If the predicted label matches the true label, the loss is 0; otherwise, it is 1, hence the name. However, this straightforward model needs more coverage of misclassified samples. Thus, it only acts as the building blocks for the primary loss functions such as exponential loss, softmax cross-entropy loss, and perceptron loss, to name a few. A more eager reader is directed to Wang et al. (2020) to delve into a comprehensive survey of loss function techniques [19].

However, for the purposes of this dissertation, one should note the following two properties of the exponential loss function. Firstly, that it produces a convex solution, meaning that the function is continuous and differentiable, therefore it can be optimised for performance. Secondly, similarly to squared loss function employed by QBoost algorithm, exponential loss function can penalise 'weak' learners that underperform and enhance overperforming stumps.

The document is organised in the following manner. In the subsequent section, i.e. *Section 2*, the reader will be familiarised with state-of-the-art of hybrid quantum-classical architectures. *Section 3* will examine the current landscape of hybrid quantum algorithms and how they can be leveraged on hybrid architectures, as discussed in *Section 2*. The experimental

procedures and results will be discussed in the penultimate section, i.e. *Section 4*. Finally, remarks and conclusions will be presented in *Section 5*.

2. Hybrid Quantum-Classical Architectures

2.1. Roadmap Towards Large-Scale Implementation

The field of quantum computation has made significant strides in recent years, particularly in the Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) era [20]. However, there are some limitations, as quantum circuits are currently constrained by a small number of qubits (typically ranging from 50-100) and noise in the quantum gates [21]. Despite these setbacks, many experts believe that NISQ computing may eventually surpass certain classical computers [21, 22]. In order to fully tap into the potential of quantum computing, one must develop more robust quantum computing architectures with a more significant number of qubits and reduced noise levels in the quantum channels.

Integrating quantum devices with their classical counterparts is challenging, mainly due to six critical aspects: number of qubits, physical differences in hardware, control and synchronisation, scalability, manufacturing, and data transfer. Furthermore, the challenges associated with integrating QPUs and CPUs may differ depending on the underlying technology used for quantum computation. We will now examine the roadmap towards large-scale implementation that will be presented in both **Table 1** and **Table 2**.

<u>Photonic technology</u>	Advantage	Drawback
Physical hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A modular scaling-up approach whereby various modules can be combined into more complex architecture. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Irregularities in cross section and waveguide, decreasing reliability of hardware. High emitter-emitter inhomogeneity.
Control & Synchronisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nano-Opto-mechanical devices displaying promise of ultra-low loss. The long-term goal of atomic scale control. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The QPU-CPU limited by an optical interface usually incompatible with modern electronics.

Scalability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wafer-scale photonic circuits promise large-scale QPU integration. 240×240 switching arrays successfully demonstrated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Photon-photon interactions become increasingly weaker with an increase in distance, limiting the number of quantum gates.
Manufacturing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Readily manufacturable; apt with CMOS circuits, most common electronics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantum dot homogeneity is required to maintain the high precision of devices.
Data transfer modes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many degrees of freedom, e.g. polarisation, entanglement, teleportation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No-cloning theorem prevents straightforward solutions for quantum networks need for quantum error correction.

<u>Ion Trap technology</u>	Advantage	Drawback
Physical hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Surface-electrode trap technology allows more dense packing of qubits on a chip. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ion-qubit coupling decoherence can pose a serious obstacle in the implementation.
Control & Synchronisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By precisely manipulating trapped ions one can achieve high fidelity quantum gates. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Noise-impaired quantum memory limits qubit and gate fidelities, effect significant for larger ensembles.
Scalability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modular approach appears to be a potential solution towards tackling the scalability issues. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult to scale up, must precisely track numerous qubits, increasingly challenging with increasing register.

Manufacturing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modular ion trap systems allow feasible integration with current technologies and are reproducible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qubit reproducibility, non-uniform ion-qubit coupling, trap heating control, low manufacturing yield.
Data transfer modes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entangling gates linking together neighbouring ions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimising loss during photon extraction, qubit-frequency mismatches.

<u>Superconductive technology</u>	Advantage	Drawback
Physical hardware	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well-controlled qubit interactions lead to entangling gates and multi-qubit operations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hardware requires dilution refrigeration to display superconductive properties.
Control & Synchronisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-speed quantum gate operations aided by qubit magnetic field interactions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qubits tend to be large, hence difficult to tune and susceptible to decoherence.
Scalability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well-understood chip fabrication process leads to scalable, high-quality chips in the near future. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More qubits, hence more decoherence and lower stability of the chips, need more sophisticated control mechanisms.
Manufacturing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well-understood reproducible microfabrication process used for the production of semiconductors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The complexity of fabricating and integrating components at nanoscale precision impacts device yield.
Data transfer modes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-speed and long-range communication, secure quantum information transfer. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qubits tend to be large, hence difficult to tune and susceptible to decoherence.

Table 1. Provides an overview of both challenges as well as optimistic perspectives for most prominent technologies employed for development and integration of QPUs with classical CPUs. Please note that the information displayed in the table was inspired by the following papers: photonics [23, 24], ion trap [25, 26], and superconducting [27, 28].

	<u>Photonic</u>	<u>Ion Trap</u>	<u>Superconductive</u>
Maximum number of logical qubits (quantum circuits)	Borealis QPU – 216 qb	IonQ – 32 qb	IBM Osprey – 433 qb

Table 2. An overview of the up-to-date maximal number of logical qubits for most prominent technologies employed for development and integration of QPUs with classical CPUs. Data taken from the following papers [29-31].

This overview considers the most notable technologies, highlighting their associated drawbacks and optimistic perspectives, as displayed in **Table 1** and **Table 2**. It is worth noting that these tables can be extended as required. However, for our purposes, they present a broad categorisation of the primary issues that must be resolved to integrate QPUs with CPUs effectively. A thorough comprehension of these technologies and their limitations is pivotal to advancing the field of quantum computing.

Let us delve into the ins and outs of **Tables 1** and **2** to give the reader a general impression of why these 6 features are key towards QPU-CPU integration. We will first tackle the maximum number of logical qubits, **Table 2**. As one can see, photonic and superconductive technologies have realised more logical qubits (an array of physical qubits that combined act as ensemble qubits) than ion trap technology, meaning they are equipped to handle more challenging problems. More logical qubits translate to more computational power, higher error correction rate, and greater quantum circuit depth, hence more robust quantum simulations and operations. Based on the above, one can easily conclude that, ultimately, the number of logical qubits dictates the limits of the computational capabilities and, thus, the long-term implementation of this technology.

Regarding the physical hardware perspectives in the short term, **Table 1**, the ion trap and superconductive have the upper hand against the photonic technology. Surface-electrode trap technology implemented for the ion trap processors demonstrated error-resistant quantum operations, high-fidelity gates and well-controlled qubits. This technology is ripe to succeed in small-scale quantum computation [32, 33]. However, it might be demanding to implement this technology in large-scale projects since it is difficult to scale up the QPUs. One must precisely track numerous qubits, which is increasingly challenging with increasing register size.

Nonetheless, the ongoing scientific effort towards functional quantum computers has deemed the modular approach a potential solution to the scalability issues. Monroe et al. (2013) proposed using standard semiconductor processing techniques to scale up ion trap quantum processors, allowing for larger-scale integration in quantum computing [26].

On the other hand, superconductive hardware at the current stage is being bet on by the biggest names in the industry, namely IBM, Google or Rigetti, with the potential to develop large-scale quantum processors, for instance, IBM Osprey with 433 qubit, demonstrating quantum supremacy. The main advantage of this technology is that it is readily scalable and reproducible. In addition, the hardware is characteristic for producing strong, decoherence resistant qubits. Therefore, facilitating entangling gates and multi-qubit operations. Nevertheless, superconductive technology requires expensive and unwieldy infrastructure, including dilution refrigerators, electromagnetic shielding, and ultra-high vacuum enclosures, which make its implementation challenging [6]. This technology is suitable for short-term integration, proven by recent achievements, and could play a crucial role in long-term integration.

Finally, photonic technology seems to have a large long-term potential as it also relies on modular approach that allows constructing more complex architectures from smaller building blocks. However, one must overcome the challenge of weakening photon-photon interactions, which could be critical for achieving long-term scalability. The use of quantum repeaters in the network could be a potential solution. A study by Carolan et al. (2015) showed a considerable decrease in optical circuit complexity, exemplifying integration pathways for linear optical protocols [34].

The potential for QPUs is vast, but there are obstacles to overcome before they become a daily reality. One major challenge is that QPUs require extremely low temperatures, which modern computing systems do not exhibit. Additionally, integrating quantum processors with classical processors is a relatively young discipline that requires further refinements. Therefore, we will examine how researchers attempt to incorporate QPUs within CPU architectures.

2.2. Loose Integration

This integration of quantum processing units (QPUs) involves a ‘loose’ connection to a host CPU network, achieved by remote access. A client-server model, similar to IBMQ’s cloud system [35], is illustrated in **Figure 1**. However, it is worth noting that the IBMQ does not have interconnected QPUs. The host system connects to a quantum computing (QC) server with multiple QPUs through a network interface (represented by the cloud), while classical interconnects (solid lines) enable communication between the server and the host system. In this scheme, QPUs are interconnected within the server (dashed lines), providing quantum parallelism. However, different paradigms are also viable. The main challenge is the entrance point (double-sided arrows), which allows for remote QC connection, prompt execution, synchronisation, and efficient quantum resource management. While this architecture can offer computational speed-up over traditional methods, it involves a trade-off between communication latency and acceleration [6]. The client-server model is beneficial in cases where significant computational advantage is gained, for instance, in machine learning, where effective resource management and selective data distribution are imperative for well-behaved algorithms [36]. Therefore highlighting the importance of choosing apt quantum algorithms to exploit this model successfully.

Figure 1. Depicts a multiprocessor system with a quantum computing server and QPUs connected by quantum interconnects (dashed lines), and classical interconnects (solid lines) [6]. Please note that the cloud represents both the entrance point and the control system, usually a remote platform to access QPUs within the QC.

2.2.1. Implementation of the client-server model

As previously mentioned, IBMQ is one example of client-server model implementation. Users can access quantum hardware via a cloud-based interface and simulate quantum systems employing QPUs equipped with 5 – 433 qubits, depending on the current demand. It has been demonstrated that this architecture can sustain Shor's factoring algorithm [37], which will be explained in greater detail in *section 3.2*, 1–2 qubit open systems, non-Markovian and Markovian evolutions, collision models or even showcase the proof-of-principle of entangled state generation [38], displaying the versatility of this computational architecture.

2.3. Tight Integration

Britt and Humble's recent work analyses advancements in the rapidly evolving accelerator model landscape intending to reduce communication latency and maximise computational speed-up within the hybrid network [6]. The priority is creating a unified system that alleviates the QPU hardware requirements while decreasing the latency between computational tasks. The left panel of **Figure 2** displays a shared resource model that allows multiple CPU nodes to interact with a single QPU, effectively reducing communication latency. It has been shown that the shared resource model would benefit from data aggregation since each CPU can delegate more computing-intensive tasks to be solved by QPU [6]. However, there is at least one main issue with this architecture, namely, the complex controller interface causing bottlenecks in the transmission of quantum and classical data.

The central panel showcases a modern accelerator model that adheres to the industry standards. Each CPU node is linked to its own QPU, resulting in a considerably simplified QPU interface. While quantum parallelism is feasible, the limited number of qubits in register may prevent complex computations. In *section 3.1*, we will discuss in depth divide-and-conquer algorithms that are tailored to exploiting this model.

Lastly, the right panel illustrates an accelerator model featuring linked QPUs. This design enables quantum communication and offers enhanced quantum parallelism across several QPUs compared to the earlier two models.

Figure 2. Illustrates three hybrid designs for CPU-QPU HPC architectures. The first design, shown on the left, is a shared resource model where multiple CPUs share a single QPU. In the centre, a standard accelerator model with each CPU connected to a QPU. Finally, the structure on the right is an accelerator model with interconnected QPUs, allowing for both quantum and classical parallelism and significant quantum distribution. Note that the dashed lines indicate a link between QPUs [6].

2.3.1. Implementation of the accelerator model

In literature, one can stumble across various efforts towards integrating CPUs with QPUs within the framework of the accelerator model; some of them are theoretical, whilst others have managed to build real-life quantum hardware. The former has been addressed by Britt et al. (2017), where the authors dive into the technical concepts and requirements towards this kind of integration. They underline the necessary kernels designed to offload the overhead present in the network so that the computational infrastructure is compatible with modern-day HPC architectures [39].

The latter has been demonstrated by D-Wave quantum annealers, which offer a significantly different approach to gate-based calculations. Instead, quantum annealers operate by evolving the quantum state about its ground state energy, hence finding its minimum. It is worth noting that quantum annealers have been developed to solve complex optimisation problems. Indeed, they thrive in this domain, as demonstrated by Mott et al. (2017), where quantum annealing was employed to solve the Higgs optimisation background noise problem [40] or in aerial imaging tree detection [41].

2.3.2. Implementation of the interconnected QPUs

Next, we will discuss the suggested design for an accelerator model featuring interconnected QPUs, as shown in **Figure 2**'s right panel (a tight integration system example). A paper by Dasari et al. (2016) reported a three-node quantum computing circuit using the

OpenFlow protocol, laying out a potential path for advanced quantum-classical designs. OpenFlow, renowned for its adaptability and high error tolerance, is a widely used protocol, making it vital for merging varied network layers, like those between CPUs and QPUs. Dasari et al. (2016) presented a programmable three-node quantum-classical network design concept, visualised in **Figure 3** [42]. This network features three main nodes (shown as green boxes in **Figure 3**) with classical and quantum network interface cards (CNICs and QNICs). These nodes are linked to specific network traffic pathways, coloured pink for classical and blue for quantum. These pathways lead to their respective switches. It is noteworthy to pay attention to small rectangular attachments on switches, depending on their colour (pink for classical, blue for quantum), which signify either QNICs or CNICs. The CNIC link between the switches and the OpenFlow protocol controller is an easily overlooked detail. This connection is crucial for transmitting information, as the controller can convert between quantum and classical data. This design forms a cornerstone for future studies in hybrid algorithms and architectures development.

Figure 3. Depicts the schematic design of a quantum network comprising three nodes, wherein a Software-Defined Networking (SDN) controller is linked to both the classical and quantum switches [42].

Having discussed the current state-of-the-art of hybrid architectures, we are in a position to dive into quantum algorithms that would benefit from these designs. *Section 3* will discuss possible implementations of the aforementioned hybrid systems.

3. Hybrid Quantum Algorithms

3.1. QAOA and VQE algorithms

According to Shaydulin et al. (2019), the effectiveness of CPUs and QPUs varies depending on the problem being solved [43]. The researchers suggest that CPUs are particularly proficient at storing and retrieving data thanks to their extensive registers, which offer greater reliability than QPUs for more extensive periods. Nevertheless, QPUs are better tailored to tackling optimisation problems, an essential step in quantum-classical hybrid algorithms. Typically, these algorithms employ CPUs to break down the problem into smaller components, which are then refined and solved by QPUs before being reassembled by the CPU to arrive at the global solution.

Quantum-classical hybrid algorithms, such as quantum approximate optimisation algorithm (QAOA) and variational quantum eigensolver (VQE), have been introduced to leverage both classical and quantum advantage as discussed above to gain algorithmic speed-up [44]. The former works by initially encoding the problem in the Hamiltonian basis. Then, the system is perturbed by the so-called mixing Hamiltonian, and it evolves. By carefully adjusting the variational parameters, i.e. the optimisation constraints, one can iteratively solve the problem so that after each iteration, the approximation approaches a more accurate solution [45]. The latter algorithm works on a similar premise; instead of optimisation techniques to find the approximate solution, it usually uses kinetic and interaction energy terms such as electron-electron and nuclear-electron interaction to search for ground-state energy solution [46]. As one can conclude, the VQE algorithm is primarily employed to solve quantum chemistry problems, whilst QAOA has been demonstrated for the travelling salesman NP-hard problem [47].

VQE and QAOA are aptly suited for execution on the conventional accelerator model depicted in **Figure 2**'s central panel. Peruzzo et al. (2014) demonstrated that they achieved computational acceleration using the VQE algorithm on photonic QPUs interfaced with CPUs, mocking a standard accelerator configuration [48], emphasising the usefulness of 'divide-and-conquer' strategies that utilise domain decomposition. These strategies fragment the primary issue into more manageable subproblems, addressing them individually to deduce a holistic solution [43]. Consequently, both QAOA and VQE illustrate the divide-and-conquer approach that can be integrated into the conventional accelerator framework.

Chalumuri et al. (2021) took this approach one step further by creating a quantum-classical machine learning algorithm for multi-class classification [49]. According to the

researchers, their hybrid model not only surpassed existing methods in terms of classification accuracy but also drastically reduced the computational resources and time required. These findings hold great potential for addressing various multi-class classification challenges, such as those encountered in natural language processing or image recognition.

3.2. Shor's algorithm

Shor's algorithm is a quantum computing breakthrough with the potential to solve the intractable task of finding prime factors of a composite integer. The algorithm randomly chooses a co-prime number and uses the quantum Fourier transform to determine its prime factors [50]. This algorithm could make traditional cryptographic systems, like RSA, outdated. Nevertheless, current quantum hardware limitations, like decoherence and an insufficient number of qubits, make it difficult to scale up the problem.

Yimsiriwattana et al.'s (2004) study explores the potential of distributing Shor's algorithm on a hybrid architecture, as illustrated in **Figure 2** on the right hand side. This architecture features interconnected QPUs that fully utilise all available qubits, making it a resource-efficient option. Although the authors acknowledge that a more complex quantum circuit can lead to additional overhead, they remain optimistic about the future of distributed quantum computing [51].

Amico et al. (2019) utilised IBMQ experience, i.e. cloud-based quantum computing platform, an example of the client-server model as discussed in *section 2.2*, to demonstrate a simplified version of Shor's algorithm [37]. Despite their efforts to showcase large-scale algorithmic implementation, they could not overcome the hardware challenges arising from the complexity of the quantum circuit. Nonetheless, the authors report that they could only run a small-scale simulation $N = 15$ that yielded excellent agreement with theoretical values. Unfortunately, the model would diverge from the theoretical predictions for larger N values. It has been suggested that more theoretical analysis should be done to tackle the hardware defects that ultimately limit the performance of quantum processors.

3.3. Variational quantum-classical algorithms for client-server model outlook

The recent work conducted by Karalekas et al. (2020) constitutes a significant milestone in making quantum computing more readily accessible and proficient not only for researchers but also potentially for institutions [52]. The development of the quantum cloud platforms is being discussed, based on the Rigetti quantum cloud, to facilitate variational

hybrid algorithms. The paper addresses critical challenges such as latency, efficiency of the network, and resource management. The authors argue that by implementing a specific reset protocol for qubits, they observed a tenfold faster network response time, hence alleviating some overhead.

Similarly, the paper by Perelshtein et al. (2022) delves into the practical application-specific benefits of hybrid quantum computing [53]. The study reveals that hybrid quantum algorithms can provide practical advantages for specific applications, such as quantum sensing, even with the current limitations of quantum hardware. While universal quantum advantage may still be unattainable, there are already specific applications where quantum computing can provide tangible benefits.

Despite the progress made, significant challenges still need to be addressed. Both papers emphasise the importance of optimising the interaction between quantum and classical processors and managing the limited coherence time of the qubits. The work by Perelshtein et al. (2022) also highlights that the advantages of hybrid quantum computing are currently application-specific, which means that further investigation is necessary to develop algorithms that can provide broader advantage.

4. Experimental Results

4.1. Methodology

Having discussed in detail the background information on quantum computing architectures and algorithms that would benefit from these designs, we are in a position to begin discussing the moot point of this dissertation, i.e. the experiment and the investigation results. We will first tackle the experimental procedure employed to harvest the data. As mentioned in *section 1.1*, we have utilised the power of quantum annealers developed by D-Wave Systems Inc. to run the QBoost algorithm. In order to benchmark the performance of the QBoost, we would train the AdaBoost algorithm described in *section 1.1* on the same dataset. In our investigation, we have selected three binary classification datasets to investigate the performance of the accelerator model architecture: Sklearn Wisconsin Breast Cancer, Bank Fraud Detection, and Surgical Deepnet datasets, all of which can be retrieved from GitHub repository [54]. The relevant information pertaining to the chosen datasets is displayed in **Table 3**.

Dataset name	Number of samples	Number of features
Wisconsin Breast Cancer	569	30
Surgical Deepnet	14,635	24
Bank Fraud Detection	20,468	112

Table 3. Overview of the datasets used in the investigation.

As one can see, we have chosen datasets primarily based on increasing the number of samples and varying the number of features. The first dataset that started the exploration was the simplest one, i.e. Wisconsin Breast Cancer. In order to train the model, we forked the QBoost package available as an open-source repository on GitHub, obtaining access to cloud-based hybrid solvers developed by D-Wave Leap Systems. The Python script developed to conduct the research is accessible under the following reference [54].

After downloading the desired dataset, the Python script would execute simple data preprocessing, such as dividing the dataset into training and testing data, shuffling the indices to minimise any statistical error from creeping into the process, and normalising the feature size lest we make systematic errors. Then, QBoost would be initiated, the request to solve the classification problem would be sent to D-Wave Leap, and after the execution of the program, the results would be sent back to the local machine. Since we had limited access to the quantum hardware, such that we would only get a small number of seconds to perform tasks on D-Wave, 30s of computational power to be exact, we had to optimise the number of iterations we could run to obtain statistically significant sample size and also not run out of time. Using a trial and error approach, we determined that an optimal number of 50 iterations would result in a big enough sample size whilst not sacrificing much precious computational time.

A similar approach was implemented for AdaBoost, though the whole program was executed on the local machine. The following metrics have been employed to evaluate the performance: accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score. Accuracy measures how well the algorithm handles the classification problem, i.e. how many instances were correctly classified versus the total number of samples. Despite being a crucial performance indicator, accuracy is insufficient to probe some dataset biases in case of binary classification problems, e.g. an uneven distribution of 1s and 0s, that ultimately skews the utility of an algorithm on its own.

Indeed, to address these challenges, precision and recall have been introduced. The former is the measure of how precise the algorithm can classify 1s as 1s and 0s as 0s, leading to the following equation: $precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$, where TP (true positive) refers to 1 being

classified as 1, and FP (false positive) means 0 being classified as 1. Similarly, recall is a measure of how many 1s were true 1s and the number of false negative cases (FN), i.e. 1s classified as 0s, leading to a similar fraction: $recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$. These metrics are complementary, and increasing one usually comes at the cost of the other. That is where the F1 score comes into play. It is a metric that combines both precision and recall values. However, F1 is not simply an arithmetic average of these values. Instead, a harmonic average is calculated, heavily penalising discrepancies between precision and recall. Finally, the runtime of the predictive model and the model in general, i.e. from initiation to the completion, have been recorded to benchmark performance. Once the relevant data was retrieved, we would change datasets and repeat the above-described process.

4.2. Four Metrics Discussion

Having described the experimental procedure, one can delve into the experimental results. We will begin by displaying the experimental results in the form of box-and-whiskers diagrams from all three normalised datasets.

Figure 4. Experimental results for the Wisconsin Breast Cancer (top panel), Surgical Deepnet (middle panel) and Fraud Detection datasets (bottom panel) are displayed as box-and-whiskers diagrams. The investigated

benchmarking metrics are displayed at the bottom of the graph, whilst the abbreviated names of algorithms are shown at the top, i.e. Ada (AdaBoost) and QB (QBoost). The range on the left-hand side has no units. It merely represents a score value between 0.00-1.00, where 0 means 0% and 1 means 100%. The numeric values displayed above the upper limit of the range represent the mean values, i.e. the white circle values within the box plots. The values are displayed in this manner to aid the clarity of graphs. Finally, the data size to create the box-and-whiskers diagrams was 50 for all datasets. Please note, in the bottom panel, i.e. Fraud Detection dataset; there is a break to facilitate displaying all four metrics at once.

Let us begin the discussion with the accuracy metric. Notably, throughout this discussion, we will primarily refer to the mean values in **Figure 4** (white circles within the box plots). As with machine learning problems, a level of variance is involved in harvesting the data. As seen across all three accuracy measurements on all datasets, QBoost underperformed compared with AdaBoost. These differences are more visible for larger datasets, i.e. the middle and bottom panel of **Figure 4**. Otgonbaatar et al. (2021) also reported an underperforming QBoost algorithm compared with its classical counterpart AdaBoost investigating Pines Hyperspectral Image dataset (HSI), with approximately 21,000 samples and 220 features, making it the closest related to, in our case, Fraud Detection [55].

Similarly, for the F1 score, we observed that QBoost tends to lag behind AdaBoost. As discussed in the *Methodology section 4.1*, the F1 score is a harmonic average of precision and recall. Thus, one should discuss precision and recall scores in conjunction with F1. Now, let us have a closer look at precision. Based on data from **Figure 4**, one may realise that in two out of three cases, the precision of QBoost would surpass AdaBoost, meaning that there were very few misclassified 0s as 1s, hence a low FP number, suggesting that one should check if the dataset is unbalanced to see if this behaviour arisen from the dominance of 1s over zeroes.

Dataset name	Number of 0s	Number of 1s
Wisconsin Breast Cancer	357	212
Surgical Deepnet	10,945	3,690
Bank Fraud Detection	15,030	5,438

Table 4. Overview of the datasets used in the investigation: division of samples classified as 1s and 0s.

According to **Table 4**, 0s dominate all datasets, ruling out our previous hypothesis that the high precision originated from 1s dominance. Another possible explanation could be that the regularisation parameter for QBoost could have emphasised overfitting 1s instances that led to high precision values for the Wisconsin Breast Cancer and Surgical Deepnet datasets whilst sacrificing the recall in the process. Wisconsin Breast Cancer provides comparable

results across all metrics. However, the dataset is small and designed so that most algorithms can easily handle classifying the problem.

4.3. Need for Speed

Now, we will discuss the algorithmic speed-up advantage of employing QBoost on quantum annealers instead of running AdaBoost on classical architectures.

Figure 5. Experimental results for the Wisconsin Breast Cancer (top panel), Surgical Deepnet (middle panel) and Fraud Detection datasets (bottom panel) are displayed as box-and-whiskers diagrams. The prediction runtimes are displayed at the bottom of the graph, whilst the names of algorithms are shown at the top. The numeric values displayed next to the white circle represent the mean values, expressed in ms. The data size to create the box-and-whiskers diagrams was 50 for all datasets. Please note that all panels have a break to facilitate displaying the runtimes. The bottom panel, i.e. the Fraud Detection dataset, has a logarithmic scale.

The first thing that might have caught the reader's attention is that, unlike in the previous *section 4.2*, where AdaBoost seemed to have the upper hand in virtually all discussed metrics across the investigated datasets, QBoost purports to be the king of speed, or rather; quantum annealers appear to offer significant computational speed-up. Indeed, we see that in all considered datasets, QBoost prevails, and the computational advantage becomes increasingly visible with increasing the dataset size. Surprisingly, QBoost can execute a program the quickest for the most extensive dataset, i.e. Fraud Detection, the bottom panel of **Figure 5**. As documented by Góes et al. (2023), a modified QBoost algorithm utilised for regression problems would complete the predictions with high accuracy within 2 ms, which is in good agreement with our experimental results [56]. On the other hand, AdaBoost prediction runtimes appear to match the following trend: the bigger the dataset, the longer the execution time, which is a well-documented phenomenon in literature [57]. Even with just 3 datasets that are not particularly large, one can see what quantum computing is all about. The immense

computational speed gain is apparent and very promising for the future of quantum computation.

What about the latency between the host and the server? When initiating the program, one sends a request to the server to solve the problem on quantum annealers. Only then can one receive back the results, begging the question: Is it worth it? As previously mentioned, not only did we record the prediction times, but we also measured the whole execution of the program presented in **Table 5**.

Dataset name	QBoost script execution	AdaBoost script execution
Wisconsin Breast Cancer	$15,166 \pm 1,218$ ms	52.2 ± 1.3 ms
Surgical Deepnet	$16,294 \pm 1,047$ ms	181 ± 3 ms
Bank Fraud Detection	$16,850 \pm 1,170$ ms	$3,338 \pm 212$ ms

Table 5. Average execution times of QBoost and AdaBoost scripts. The errors were calculated using standard deviations using data from 50 iterations.

Regarding the data in **Table 5**, one can easily see that the execution times for the QBoost program fall within a similar timeframe. In contrast, AdaBoost requires more and more time to process the script as the difficulty of the datasets scales up. However, the total execution time is orders of magnitude shorter than for QBoost, which leads us to conclude that it might not be feasible to use QBoost for small datasets since the computational speed-up is outweighed by colossal latency. In addition, as demonstrated in the previous section, AdaBoost, in general, is better behaved, as evidenced by accuracy and F1 scores displayed in **Figure 4**. Once the latency issues are addressed, we can strive to exploit algorithmic speed-up and aim for quantum supremacy.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, we surveyed contemporary advancements in the quantum computing landscape. We covered potential pathways towards integrating QPUs with modern-day HPC architectures, which can be separated into loose and tight integration classes. Furthermore, we proposed a road map classifier that highlights the development of the three most commonly used technologies: photonic, ion trap, and superconducting. Their perspectives and limitations were evaluated across six categories: number of qubits, hardware differences, control and synchronisation, scalability, manufacturing, and data transfer. In addition, hybrid algorithms have been covered and assigned to dedicated quantum-classical architectures to realise the quantum advantage.

In the second part of the report, we discussed metrics necessary to benchmark the performance of hybrid architectures, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1. We demonstrated that in the near term, quantum advantage can be gained primarily in computational speed-up. However, communication latency limits the utility of cloud-based systems for small-scale machine-learning hybrid algorithms. Once these challenges are overcome, the quantum potential can be realised.

For future work, we suggest exploring other architectures, such as shared resource or interconnected accelerator models with algorithms, as discussed in *Section 3*. Perhaps extending our line of research with additional datasets and more sophisticated preprocessing techniques to potentially better understand the root problem seen in recall and precision.

References

- [1] B. Pokharel, D.A. Lidar, Demonstration of algorithmic quantum speedup, arXiv preprint arXiv:2207.07647, DOI (2022).
- [2] P.W. Shor, Algorithms for quantum computation: discrete logarithms and factoring, Proceedings 35th annual symposium on foundations of computer science, Ieee, 1994, pp. 124-134.
- [3] I. Kassal, J.D. Whitfield, A. Perdomo-Ortiz, M.-H. Yung, A. Aspuru-Guzik, Simulating Chemistry Using Quantum Computers, Annual Review of Physical Chemistry, 62 (2011) 185-207.
- [4] D. Cuomo, M. Caleffi, A.S. Cacciapuoti, Towards a distributed quantum computing ecosystem, IET Quantum Communication, 1 (2020) 3-8.
- [5] F. Arute, K. Arya, R. Babbush, D. Bacon, J.C. Bardin, R. Barends, R. Biswas, S. Boixo, F. Brandao, D.A. Buell, B. Burkett, Y. Chen, Z. Chen, B. Chiaro, R. Collins, W. Courtney, A. Dunsworth, E. Farhi, B. Foxen, A. Fowler, C. Gidney, M. Giustina, R. Graff, K. Guerin, S. Habegger, M.P. Harrigan, M.J. Hartmann, A. Ho, M. Hoffmann, T. Huang, T.S. Humble, S.V. Isakov, E. Jeffrey, Z. Jiang, D. Kafri, K. Kechedzhi, J. Kelly, P.V. Klimov, S. Knysh, A. Korotkov, F. Kostritsa, D. Landhuis, M. Lindmark, E. Lucero, D. Lyakh, S. Mandrà, J.R. McClean, M. McEwen, A. Megrant, X. Mi, K. Michielsen, M. Mohseni, J. Mutus, O. Naaman, M. Neeley, C. Neill, M.Y. Niu, E. Ostby, A. Petukhov, J.C. Platt, C. Quintana, E.G. Rieffel, P. Roushan, N.C. Rubin, D. Sank, K.J. Satzinger, V. Smelyanskiy, K.J. Sung, M.D. Trevithick, A. Vainsencher, B. Villalonga, T. White, Z.J. Yao, P. Yeh, A. Zalcman, H. Neven, J.M. Martinis, Quantum supremacy using a programmable superconducting processor, Nature, 574 (2019) 505-510.
- [6] K.A. Britt, T.S. Humble, High-Performance Computing with Quantum Processing Units, J. Emerg. Technol. Comput. Syst., 13 (2017) Article 39.
- [7] L. Chen, X. Huo, G. Agrawal, Accelerating MapReduce on a coupled CPU-GPU architecture, SC '12: Proceedings of the International Conference on High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis, 2012, pp. 1-11.
- [8] T. El-Ghazawi, E. El-Araby, M. Huang, K. Gaj, V. Kindratenko, D. Buell, The Promise of High-Performance Reconfigurable Computing, Computer, 41 (2008) 69-76.

- [9] B.I. Schneider, The Impact of Heterogeneous Computer Architectures on Computational Physics, *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 17 (2015) 9-13.
- [10] R. Lucas, J. Ang, K. Bergman, S. Borkar, W. Carlson, L. Carrington, G. Chiu, R. Colwell, W. Dally, J. Dongarra, A. Geist, R. Haring, J. Hittinger, A. Hoisie, D.M. Klein, P. Kogge, R. Lethin, V. Sarkar, R. Schreiber, J. Shalf, T. Sterling, R. Stevens, J. Bashor, R. Brightwell, P. Coteus, E. Debenedictus, J. Hiller, K.H. Kim, H. Langston, R.M. Murphy, C. Webster, S. Wild, G. Grider, R. Ross, S. Leyffer, J. Laros Iii, DOE Advanced Scientific Computing Advisory Subcommittee (ASCAC) Report: Top Ten Exascale Research Challenges, United States, 2014.
- [11] A. Geist, R. Lucas, Major Computer Science Challenges At Exascale, *The International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications*, 23 (2009) 427-436.
- [12] R.E. Schapire, Explaining adaboost, *Empirical Inference: Festschrift in Honor of Vladimir N. Vapnik*, Springer 2013, pp. 37-52.
- [13] H. Neven, V.S. Denchev, G. Rose, W.G. Macready, Training a binary classifier with the quantum adiabatic algorithm, arXiv preprint arXiv:0811.0416, DOI (2008).
- [14] H. Neven, V.S. Denchev, G. Rose, W.G. Macready, Qboost: Large scale classifier training with adiabatic quantum optimization, *Asian Conference on Machine Learning*, PMLR, 2012, pp. 333-348.
- [15] C.F. Higham, D.J. Higham, F. Tudisco, Testing a QUBO formulation of core-periphery partitioning on a quantum annealer, arXiv preprint arXiv:2201.01543, DOI (2022).
- [16] J. Li, S. Ghosh, Quantum-soft qubo suppression for accurate object detection, *European Conference on Computer Vision*, Springer, 2020, pp. 158-173.
- [17] R. Quintero, D. Bernal, T. Terlaky, L.F. Zuluaga, Characterization of QUBO reformulations for the maximum k-colorable subgraph problem, *Quantum Information Processing*, 21 (2022) 89.
- [18] T. Hastie, S. Rosset, J. Zhu, H. Zou, Multi-class adaboost, *Statistics and its Interface*, 2 (2009) 349-360.
- [19] Q. Wang, Y. Ma, K. Zhao, Y. Tian, A comprehensive survey of loss functions in machine learning, *Annals of Data Science*, DOI (2020) 1-26.
- [20] J.W.Z. Lau, K.H. Lim, H. Shrotriya, L.C. Kwek, NISQ computing: where are we and where do we go?, *AAPPS Bulletin*, 32 (2022) 27.
- [21] J. Preskill, Quantum computing in the NISQ era and beyond, *Quantum*, 2 (2018) 79.
- [22] B. Villalonga, D. Lyakh, S. Boixo, H. Neven, T.S. Humble, R. Biswas, E.G. Rieffel, A. Ho, S. Mandrà, Establishing the quantum supremacy frontier with a 281 pflop/s simulation, *Quantum Science and Technology*, 5 (2020) 034003.
- [23] J. Wang, F. Sciarrino, A. Laing, M.G. Thompson, Integrated photonic quantum technologies, *Nature Photonics*, 14 (2020) 273-284.
- [24] R. Uppu, L. Midolo, X. Zhou, J. Carolan, P. Lodahl, Single-photon quantum hardware: towards scalable photonic quantum technology with a quantum advantage, arXiv preprint arXiv:2103.01110, DOI (2021).
- [25] C.D. Bruzewicz, J. Chiaverini, R. McConnell, J.M. Sage, Trapped-ion quantum computing: Progress and challenges, *Applied Physics Reviews*, 6 (2019) 021314.
- [26] C. Monroe, J. Kim, Scaling the Ion Trap Quantum Processor, *Science*, 339 (2013) 1164-1169.
- [27] H.-L. Huang, D. Wu, D. Fan, X. Zhu, Superconducting quantum computing: a review, *Science China Information Sciences*, 63 (2020) 1-32.

- [28] J.M. Gambetta, J.M. Chow, M. Steffen, Building logical qubits in a superconducting quantum computing system, *npj quantum information*, 3 (2017) 2.
- [29] J. Chow, O. Dial, J. Gambetta, IBM Quantum breaks the 100-qubit processor barrier, IBM Research Blog, DOI (2021).
- [30] L.S. Madsen, F. Laudenbach, M.F. Askarani, F. Rortais, T. Vincent, J.F.F. Bulmer, F.M. Miatto, L. Neuhaus, L.G. Helt, M.J. Collins, A.E. Lita, T. Gerrits, S.W. Nam, V.D. Vaidya, M. Menotti, I. Dhand, Z. Vernon, N. Quesada, J. Lavoie, Quantum computational advantage with a programmable photonic processor, *Nature*, 606 (2022) 75-81.
- [31] C. Monroe, Ionq quantum computers: clear to scale, APS March Meeting Abstracts, 2021, pp. P10. 002.
- [32] B. Lekitsch, S. Weidt, A.G. Fowler, K. Mølmer, S.J. Devitt, C. Wunderlich, W.K. Hensinger, Blueprint for a microwave trapped ion quantum computer, *Science Advances*, 3 (2017) e1601540.
- [33] D. Allcock, Surface-electrode ion traps for scalable quantum computing, Oxford University, UK, 2011.
- [34] J. Carolan, C. Harrold, C. Sparrow, E. Martín-López, N.J. Russell, J.W. Silverstone, P.J. Shadbolt, N. Matsuda, M. Oguma, M. Itoh, G.D. Marshall, M.G. Thompson, J.C.F. Matthews, T. Hashimoto, J.L. O'Brien, A. Laing, Universal linear optics, *Science*, 349 (2015) 711-716.
- [35] S.-J. Wei, T. Xin, G.-L. Long, Efficient universal quantum channel simulation in IBM's cloud quantum computer, *Science China Physics, Mechanics & Astronomy*, 61 (2018) 70311.
- [36] M. Schuld, I. Sinayskiy, F. Petruccione, An introduction to quantum machine learning, *Contemporary Physics*, 56 (2015) 172-185.
- [37] M. Amico, Z.H. Saleem, M. Kumph, Experimental study of Shor's factoring algorithm using the IBM Q Experience, *Physical Review A*, 100 (2019) 012305.
- [38] G. García-Pérez, M.A. Rossi, S. Maniscalco, IBM Q Experience as a versatile experimental testbed for simulating open quantum systems, *npj Quantum Information*, 6 (2020) 1.
- [39] K.A. Britt, F.A. Mohiyaddin, T.S. Humble, Quantum accelerators for high-performance computing systems, 2017 IEEE International Conference on Rebooting Computing (ICRC), IEEE, 2017, pp. 1-7.
- [40] A. Mott, J. Job, J.-R. Vlimant, D. Lidar, M. Spiropulu, Solving a Higgs optimization problem with quantum annealing for machine learning, *Nature*, 550 (2017) 375-379.
- [41] E. Boyda, S. Basu, S. Ganguly, A. Michaelis, S. Mukhopadhyay, R.R. Nemani, Deploying a quantum annealing processor to detect tree cover in aerial imagery of California, *PloS one*, 12 (2017) e0172505.
- [42] V. Dasari, R. Sadlier, R. Prout, B. Williams, T. Humble, Programmable multi-node quantum network design and simulation, SPIE2016.
- [43] R. Shaydulin, H. Ushijima-Mwesigwa, C.F. Negre, I. Safro, S.M. Mniszewski, Y. Alexeev, A hybrid approach for solving optimization problems on small quantum computers, *Computer*, 52 (2019) 18-26.
- [44] K. Phalak, A. Ash-Saki, M. Alam, R.O. Topaloglu, S. Ghosh, Quantum puf for security and trust in quantum computing, *IEEE Journal on Emerging and Selected Topics in Circuits and Systems*, 11 (2021) 333-342.
- [45] J. Choi, J. Kim, A tutorial on quantum approximate optimization algorithm (QAOA): Fundamentals and applications, 2019 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC), IEEE, 2019, pp. 138-142.
- [46] M. Qing, W. Xie, Use VQE to calculate the ground energy of hydrogen molecules on IBM Quantum, arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.06538, DOI (2023).

- [47] Y. Ruan, S. Marsh, X. Xue, Z. Liu, J. Wang, The quantum approximate algorithm for solving traveling salesman problem, *Computers, Materials and Continua*, 63 (2020) 1237-1247.
- [48] A. Peruzzo, J. McClean, P. Shadbolt, M.-H. Yung, X.-Q. Zhou, P.J. Love, A. Aspuru-Guzik, J.L. O'Brien, A variational eigenvalue solver on a photonic quantum processor, *Nature communications*, 5 (2014) 4213.
- [49] A. Chalumuri, R. Kune, B. Manoj, A hybrid classical-quantum approach for multi-class classification, *Quantum Information Processing*, 20 (2021) 119.
- [50] P.W. Shor, Polynomial-time algorithms for prime factorization and discrete logarithms on a quantum computer, *SIAM review*, 41 (1999) 303-332.
- [51] A. Yimsiriwattana, S.J. Lomonaco Jr, Distributed quantum computing: A distributed Shor algorithm, *Quantum Information and Computation II*, SPIE, 2004, pp. 360-372.
- [52] P.J. Karalekas, N.A. Tezak, E.C. Peterson, C.A. Ryan, M.P. Da Silva, R.S. Smith, A quantum-classical cloud platform optimized for variational hybrid algorithms, *Quantum Science and Technology*, 5 (2020) 024003.
- [53] M. Perelshtein, A. Sagingalieva, K. Pinto, V. Shete, A. Pakhomchik, A. Melnikov, F. Neukart, G. Gesek, A. Melnikov, V. Vinokur, Practical application-specific advantage through hybrid quantum computing, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2205.04858*, DOI (2022).
- [54] S. Grodek, Masters project, https://github.com/Stanisla0/Masters_Project, accessed 07.09.23.
- [55] S. Otgonbaatar, M. Datcu, A quantum annealer for subset feature selection and the classification of hyperspectral images, *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 14 (2021) 7057-7065.
- [56] C.B. Góes, T.O. Maciel, G.G. Pollachini, J.P. Salazar, R.G. Cuenca, E.I. Duzzioni, QBoost for regression problems: solving partial differential equations, *Quantum Information Processing*, 22 (2023) 129.
- [57] R. Wang, AdaBoost for feature selection, classification and its relation with SVM, a review, *Physics Procedia*, 25 (2012) 800-807.